

Figure S146. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) predicted mean weekly **SO₂** volume mixing ratio (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (d) FAC2, and (e) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS, CAPMoN, CASTNet, and NAPS stations.

Figure S151. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) predicted mean hourly **PM_{2.5}-SO₄** concentration (µg m⁻³) and (c) NMB, (d) FAC2, and (e) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations.

Figure S158. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) predicted mean weekly **SO₄⁻ concentration-in-precipitation** (mg L⁻¹) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CAPMoN and NADP stations.

Figure S162. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) predicted mean weekly **SO₄⁻ wet deposition** (mg m⁻²) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CAPMoN and NADP stations.